

CRIMES RELATED TO CORRUPTION

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Abstract Since the early days of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, economic sectors have been radically reformed, freedom has been given on a large scale, and the fight against crimes in this sector has also been raised to the level of state policy. In turn, the laws on liability for crimes in this area were fundamentally changed. The essence of these changes came from the social danger of crimes in the economic sphere.

Keywords: Criminal law, Crimes related, various criminal acts, corruption-related crimes, UN Secretary, excessive regulations.

Corruption, which is one of the global problems that is developing today and is increasingly worrying the representatives of the world community, is one of the evils that hinders the security and stability of society, social, economic development and the institutional development of the government. Crimes related to corruption not only damage the reputation of government representatives in front of the society, but also cause a serious problem in the effective establishment of internal and external political, economic and social relations. Corruption is not a separate crime with a single composition. Criminal law provides for liability for crimes related to corruption, not for corruption. This means that corruption is a collection of several

crimes.

Analyzing the norms of the special part of the Republic of Uzbekistan JK, we can emphasize that corruption as a social phenomenon has manifested itself in various criminal acts. Including: Article 167, Part 2, Clause "g" of the Civil Code (by abuse of official position); Article 168, Part 3, Clause "v" (using the service position); Article 1929 (extortion by bribery in commerce); Article 19210 (abduction of an employee of a non-state commercial organization or other non-state organization in exchange for a bribe); Article 19211 (Abuse of authority by officials in a non-state commercial organization or other non-state organization); Article 205 (Abuse of power or authority); Article 206 (exceeding the scope of authority or authority); Article 209 (falsification of office); Article 210 (bribery); Article 211 (bribery); Article 212 (intermediary in receiving and giving bribes); Article 213 (abduction of an employee of a state body, state-participated organization or citizen self-government body in exchange for a bribe); Article 214 (Unlawful acquisition of material values or property interest by an employee of a state body, an organization with state participation, or a self-government body of citizens); Article 243 (Legalization of proceeds from criminal activities); Article 301 (Abuse of power, going beyond authority or inaction of power).

The general object of corruption crimes is the normal functioning of state authorities and administrative bodies, as well as social relations aimed at ensuring the rights and legal interests of citizens.

The nature of the crime also plays an important role in the classification of corruption-related crimes. Judging from the content of the official definition of the concept of "corruption" in Article 3 of the Law "On Combating Corruption", the purpose of corruption crimes can be not only material, but also intangible benefits.

According to the information provided by UN Secretary General A. Gutterish, cases of giving and receiving bribes in the amount of 1 trillion US dollars are made every year in the world community. It has been reported that the world economy

loses more than 2.6 trillion US dollars annually due to corruption, which is 5% of the world's gross domestic product.

If we focus on the statistics of corruption crimes at the national level, during the years 2017-2020

The issue of criminal liability of 6,127 officials was resolved. Of these, in 2018, a total of 351 (129 in 2019) were reported to officials of state-owned business entities, and 362 (401 in 2019) to officials of non-state-owned business entities in 2018.

Also, in 2017, 142 bln. 662 mln. 559 billion soums in 2018. 174 mln. soums, and 1 trillion in 2019. 853 billion material damage was caused in the amount of sums.

Corruption in India is an issue which affects economy of central, state and local government agencies in many ways. Corruption is blamed for stunting the economy of India. A study conducted by Transparency International in 2005 recorded that more than 62% of Indians had at some point or another paid a bribe to a public official to get a job done. In 2008, another report showed that about 50% of Indians had first hand experience of paying bribes or using contacts to get services performed by public offices. In 2021 their Corruption Perceptions Index ranked the country in 85th place out of 180, on a scale where the lowest-ranked countries are perceived to have the most honest public sector. Various factors contribute to corruption, including officials siphoning money from government social welfare schemes. Examples include the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act and the National Rural Health Mission. Other areas of corruption include India's trucking industry which is forced to pay billions of rupees in bribes annually to numerous regulatory and police stops on interstate highways. The causes of corruption in India include excessive regulations, complicated tax and licensing systems, numerous government departments with opaque bureaucracy and discretionary powers, monopoly of government controlled institutions on certain

goods and services delivery, and the lack of transparent laws and processes. There are significant variations in the level of corruption and in the government's efforts to reduce corruption across India.

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